

Fertilizer pollution causes diseases in plants

Rovy M Varghese

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
rovymvarghese@gmail.com

Mr. Jobin T J

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Plant diseases can be reported from those farmers who use fertilizers excessively without the ample support and instruction from authorized agriculture officers. For farmers, it can be difficult to identify the diseases and its causes and thereafter a means of prevention, and the proper medications. This project suggests a convolutional neural network (CNN)-based image recognition system that can identify plant illnesses in order to solve the problem. Farmers can get a real-time diagnosis of a disease, along with the information on its cause, prevention advice, and suggested medications, by sending clear images of affected plants to the system. With this method, farmers would have a practical and affordable tool to control the fertilizer pollution by analyzing the infected leaf image and thereby making the farmer aware of the fertilizer they have to use in order to minimize the pollution. Furthermore, the model recommends the appropriate fertilizer to the user in order to maintain a sound ecosystem for better plant health.

Keywords- CNN, classification, Deep learning, image processing, visualization

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the modern agriculture era has brought diversified crop production and quality along with new diseases and prevailing diseases too. The automated identification and diagnosis of plant diseases has become a growing area of application for computer vision techniques in recent years. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), one of these methods, have excelled in image processing and classification applications. Approaches based on CNNs provide advantages like high accuracy and resistance to noise and fluctuations in the images. They can learn intricate traits and patterns particular to plant diseases by being taught on huge databases of labeled photos. In this study, we look at how CNNs may be used to identify plant diseases, focusing on the image processing aspect of the strategy.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are image processing techniques used to identify plant diseases through a deep learning model on a collection of annotated pictures for disease presence or absence. Once trained, the model can be used to categorize new images and spot any disease symptoms. You can make advantage of this technology by adding infected plant images to the website that has been created to carry out this analysis. The website

would analyze the image and offer a diagnosis of any diseases found using the trained model. Farmers and researchers who might not have access to advanced equipment or technical expertise in image processing can still use this method because it is accessible to them. It is a helpful tool for plant disease prediction programs since it can be used to easily analyze a lot of photos. By lowering noise, adjusting brightness and contrast, and shrinking the image, pre-processing improves the image's quality. In the crucial step of feature extraction, the CNN examines the image and finds significant patterns and features that are pertinent to the issue at hand. Convolutional and pooling layers that extract progressively more intricate characteristics from the input image are used to achieve this. Complexity of the disease symptoms and the quality of the training dataset will determine how accurate the diagnosis will be, therefore more study is required to develop and advance the technology.

In general, CNN-based image processing for plant disease identification is a promising method that has the potential to completely change the agricultural sector. This method is likely to become even more precise and effective as technology develops, assisting farmers and researchers in addressing the intricate problems that face modern agriculture.

A. Image manipulation

The process of converting an image into a digital format and carrying out specific procedures to extract some usable information from it is known as image processing. When implementing certain specified signal processing techniques, the image processing system typically interprets all pictures as 2D signals.

B. CNN

A CNN is a form of deep learning network design that is used for tasks such as image recognition and pixel data processing. While the existence of other types of neural networks in deep learning, CNNs are the accepted network design for object identification and recognition.

II. IMAGE PROCESSING - CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS(CNN)

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) are trained on a large dataset of tagged images in image processing to locate and classify objects or patterns in an image. Pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification are a few of the phases that make up the process. By lowering noise, adjusting brightness and contrast, and shrinking the image, pre-processing improves the image's quality. In the crucial step of feature extraction, the CNN examines the image and finds significant patterns and features that are pertinent to the issue at hand. Convolutional and pooling layers that extract progressively more intricate characteristics from the input image are used to achieve this.

Following feature extraction, the CNN classifies the image based on the extracted features using a fully connected layer. A SoftMax function is often used to assign a probability score to each class from the output of the fully connected layer. The projected class for the input image is the one with the highest likelihood score.

In order to automatically identify and diagnose different plant diseases from photos of plant leaves, stems, or other plant parts, image processing with CNN can be utilized. This technique can aid farmers in the early detection of plant diseases, perhaps halting the disease's progress and enhancing crop output and quality.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

For crops to grow and flourish, fertilizers are crucial. But excessive and improper fertilizer use can result in fertilizer pollution, one of the biggest environmental issues on the planet. The health of plants is significantly impacted by fertilizer pollution, which also causes a number of diseases and eventually lowers agricultural productivity. The goal of this literature review is to give a general overview of how fertilizer contamination affects plant diseases.

Rashid et al. (2019),[1] Using too many chemical fertilizers in agriculture contaminates the soil, which has an adverse effect on plant health. According to the study, extended usage of fertilizers high in nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium causes an accumulation of these nutrients in the soil, which creates imbalances that might result in plant illnesses. The scientists noticed that plants growing in soil that had been intensively fertilized exhibited signs of nutrient toxicity, such as leaf chlorosis, necrosis, and wilting. According to the study, using fewer chemical fertilizers and switching to sustainable farming methods can help decrease fertilizer pollution and enhance plant health.

Sivakumar et al. (2020),[2] Studied how long-term use of chemical fertilizers affected the health of the soil and plant illnesses. According to the study, frequent application of fertilizers high in nitrogen and phosphorus caused the soil to become more acidic, which enhanced the availability of harmful metals in the soil. The scientists noticed that plants raised in such soil had indications of nutrient inadequacy and were more susceptible to fungi-related illnesses. The study

concludes that integrated nutrient management practices and routine soil health monitoring can help reduce the harmful impacts of fertilizer contamination on plant health.

Naveed et al. (2021),[3] Investigated the effects of fertilizer contamination on the development and output of wheat crops. The researchers observed that excessive use of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers not only reduced crop yield but also polluted the soil with nitrate and phosphate, which may be detrimental to humans, animals, and groundwater. Farmers, according to the paper, should use precision farming practices to optimize fertilizer consumption and reduce contamination. Hossain et al. (2020),[4] The researchers looked into how fertilizer pollution affected rice harvests. According to the study, excessive nitrogen fertilizer use resulted in a build-up of nitrate in the soil, which made rice plants more vulnerable to bacterial infections. The scientists noticed that plants cultivated in soil that had been intensively fertilized had yellowing, stunting, and root rot signs. In order to stop crop disease outbreaks, the research advises farmers to use less nitrogen fertilizer and implement integrated pest control strategies.

Liu et al. (2019),[5] Investigated how fertilizer contamination affected the microbial populations in soil. According to the study, extended use of chemical fertilizers resulted in a decrease in the diversity and number of helpful microorganisms in soil, which might have an effect on plant development and health. The scientists noticed that plants growing in such soil had symptoms of decreased nutrient absorption and disease susceptibility. According to the study, utilizing biofertilizers and switching to organic agricultural methods can assist improve soil health and encourage plant development.

Tariq et al. (2021),[6] Looked at the effects of fertilizer pollution on the development and output of maize crops. According to the study, using nitrogen fertilizers excessively caused nitrate to accumulate in the soil, making maize plants more vulnerable to fungi. The scientists discovered that plants cultivated in soil that had been intensively fertilized had signs of stunted growth, yield, and root expansion. The report advises farmers to use less nitrogen fertilizer and switch to organic farming methods in order to improve soil health and stop disease outbreaks.

Chen et al. (2021),[7] Examined the influence of soil microbiota contamination from nitrogen fertilizer on plant growth. The study discovered that the use of nitrogen fertilizers resulted in a decrease in the variety and number of helpful bacteria in soil, which might have a detrimental effect on plant development and health. The study team discovered that plants cultivated in nitrogen-polluted soil exhibited indicators of diminished nutrient absorption and higher susceptibility to illnesses. According to the report, farmers should.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The first stage in the proposed methodology is to gather a dataset of pictures of healthy and unwell plants for various crop species. To make sure that the dataset is balanced and free of duplicates and inaccurate labels, pre-processing and cleaning will be done.

```

import os
from flask import Flask, request, render_template, jsonify
from PIL import Image
import torchvision.transforms.functional as TF
import CNN
import numpy as np
import torch
import pandas as pd

disease_info = pd.read_csv('disease_info.csv', encoding='cp1252')
supplement_info = pd.read_csv('supplement_info.csv', encoding='cp1252')
model = CNN.CNN(CNN)
model.load_state_dict(torch.load('plant_disease_model_1_latest.pt'))
model.eval()

def prediction(image_path):
    image = Image.open(image_path)
    image = image.resize((224, 224))
    input_data = TF.to_tensor(image)
    input_data = input_data.view(-1, 3, 224, 224)
    output = model(input_data)
    output = output.detach().numpy()
    index = np.argmax(output)
    return index

app = Flask(__name__)
@app.route('/submit', methods=['POST'])
def submit():
    image = request.files['image']
    if image:
        filename = image.filename
        file_path = os.path.join('static/uploads', filename)
        image.save(file_path)
        pred = prediction(file_path)
        title = disease_info[disease_name][pred]
        description = disease_info[description][pred]
        prevent = disease_info['Possible Steps'][pred]
        image_url = disease_info['image_url'][pred]
        supplement_name = supplement_info[supplement_name][pred]
        supplement_image_url = supplement_info[supplement_image][pred]
        supplement_buy_link = supplement_info[supplement_buy_link][pred]
        return render_template('submit.html', title = title, desc = description, prevent = prevent,
                               image_url = image_url, price = price, name = supplement_name, simage = supplement_image_url, buy_link = supplement_buy_link)
    if __name__ == '__main__':
        app.run(debug=True)
    
```

Fig 1
The image accepted from the user is sent to the designed function using <http://localhost:5000>

Fig 2

Following that, the app will classify the input image into one of several disease categories by extracting relevant information from the image using a convolutional neural network (CNN). The remaining photos will be utilized for testing and validation, while a subset of the dataset will be used to train the CNN. To adjust the model to new crop species and disease kinds, transfer learning will be used for fine-tuning. The app will include details on the disease's description, preventative strategies, and suggested therapies once it has been detected. It will be based on reliable scientific publications and databases like the Integrated Pest Management Centre's and the Plant Health Progress.

The software will be deeply tested using a range of photos of both healthy and damaged plants in order to confirm its correctness and dependability. For quick and precise results, the app will also be speed and efficiency optimized. All things considered, this app has the potential to be a useful tool for farmers and plant enthusiasts, enabling them to quickly and reliably detect plant illnesses and take the necessary precautions to stop their spread and lessen their influence on agricultural output.

Apple : Cedar rust

Brief Description :

Cedar apple rust (*Gymnosporangium juniperi-virginianae*) is a fungal disease that requires juniper plants to complete its complicated two year life-cycle. Spores overwinter as a reddish-brown gall on young twigs of various juniper species. In early spring, during wet weather, these galls swell and bright orange masses of spores are blown by the wind where they infect susceptible apple and crab-apple trees. The spores that develop on these trees will only infect junipers the following year. From year to year, the disease must pass from junipers to apples to junipers again; it cannot spread between apple trees.

Prevent This Plant Disease By follow below steps :

Choose resistant cultivars when available. Rake up and dispose of fallen leaves and other debris from under trees. Remove galls from infected junipers. In some cases, juniper plants should be removed entirely. Apply preventative, disease-fighting fungicides labeled for use on apples weekly, starting with bud break, to protect trees from spores being released by the juniper host. This occurs only once per year, so additional applications after this springtime spread are not necessary. On juniper, rust can be controlled by spraying plants with a copper solution (0.5 to 2.0 oz/ gallon of water) at least four times between late August and late October. Safely treat most fungal and bacterial diseases with SERENADE Garden. This broad spectrum bio-fungicide uses a patented strain of *Bacillus subtilis* that is registered for organic use. Best of all, SERENADE is completely non-toxic to honey bees and beneficial insects.

Supplements :

Katyayani All in 1 Organic Fungicide

Fig 3

V. CONCLUSION

Fertilizer pollution is a serious environmental problem with multiple harmful consequences for both plant and human health. The influence of excessive fertilizer usage on plants has been highlighted in this literature study, which can lead to the appearance of numerous illnesses. Nutrient buildup in soil, such as nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium can cause an imbalance in the soil ecology, allowing undesirable microbes and illnesses to proliferate.

In addition, the study emphasized the necessity of prudent fertilizer management practices in mitigating the detrimental consequences of fertilizer contamination. Reduced fertilizer usage, precise farming techniques, and the use of alternative fertilizers such as organic matter are all examples of effective management practices. Furthermore, soil testing can provide valuable insights into crop nutrient needs, which can aid in avoiding over-fertilization. Furthermore, the proposed app, which employs machine learning algorithms, has the potential to be a valuable tool for farmers and plant enthusiasts in diagnosing plant diseases and implementing appropriate preventative measures. This strategy might assist to reduce the harmful effects of fertilizer contamination while also maintaining healthy and sustainable agricultural production systems.

Overall, ongoing research and innovation in fertilizer management practices are vital to mitigating the harmful effects of fertilizer pollution and encouraging sustainable agricultural practices. By applying suitable management practices and utilizing modern technology, we can ensure the long-term health of our soil, plants, and ecosystems.

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